

Village Government Governance in an Effort to Improve Public Services

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Abstract:- This research examines the governance of Gantarang Village government located in Sinjai Tengah Sub-district with a focus on improving public services. The purpose of this research is to understand how the governance of Gantarang Village government contributes to the improvement of public services. The method used was qualitative with a descriptive approach. Data collection was conducted through observation, interviews with village officials, community leaders, and service users, coupled with documentation studies. Data analysis was conducted using data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing techniques. The results showed that the governance of the Gantarang Village government in improving public services has reached a fairly good level. This can be seen from the implementation of programmes and policies that are responsive to community needs, transparency in budget management and public information, and active community participation in the decision-making process.

Keywords:- Village Governance, Public Services, Gantarang Village, Central Sinjai.

I. INTRODUCTION

Good and quality services have implications for community satisfaction, because the community directly evaluates the performance of the services provided, good service and good quality are the basis of community

satisfaction. For this reason, public services can be said to be efficient if the community enjoys the convenience of services in a short, fast, precise and satisfying procedure in article 17 of Law No. 25 of 2009 concerning Public Services used as a guideline for service delivery and as a reference for quality assessment (Azzahra, 2023).

But in reality, the current state of public services, according to experience, has been complex, slow, expensive, difficult to implement, weak and tired, so it is still not as efficient and effective as expected. This can be seen from the many complaints and appeals from the public, both directly and indirectly. This tendency occurs because the community has not been positioned as the "Service" party. This has a negative impact on the development of service quality. That is, neglected efforts to improve services, lack of service activation development and lack of government incentives to improve service quality (Reddy and Brumpton, 2021).

Public services provide a more visible measure of government performance. The quality of public services is of great concern to many people, and people from all disciplines can directly feel the impact, so people can directly judge government performance based on the perceived quality of service. I can do it. And it is my responsibility to strengthen the positive image of the government in the eyes of the community. In this regard, Gantarang Village, as the closest government organisation

directly in contact with the community, promotes the successful development of municipal autonomy, especially the region, and Gantarang Village is directly involved in development and renovation planning and services. For this reason, the Gantarang Village Office must be able to serve as a platform where the community can integrate their aspirations, and those aspirations and communicate them to stakeholders for follow-up. In addition, the role of Gantarang Village is to socialise government programmes to the community for their understanding and support. Influencing these issues is about the opportunity to improve their skills and empower them professionally so that they can identify good and bad services from the village itself (Djou, et al., 2023). Therefore, the operation of village craft equipment requires skills and motivation to achieve task outcomes and provide quality services to the community (Honig, 2022).

Based on the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 6 of 2014, this Law regulates the duties, functions and authorities of the Village in carrying out government and development at the village level. Besides that the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 6 of 2014, also includes provisions related to public servants at the village level, where in this Law there are several points related to administrative services, administrative services are regulated in article 18 to article 21, in these articles it confirms the obligations of the village in organising services to the community, including civil registration services, population documents, and other administrations needed by the village community (Yustisia, 2015).

Referring to the explanation of the Law on Villages above, it is a strong enough legal basis to see how the governance of the gantaran village government in the middle sinjai sub-district of sinjai district in improving public services in the village and based on preliminary observations made by the author obtained information that will be sought for truth when conducting further research later, where information obtained from the Head of Gantarang Village said that the services at the gantarang village office were quite good and the time of administrative services and the like provided to the community did not need to use a long time (Saputra, et al, 2024).

Some supporting research on governance and public service research includes a study that aims to analyse the public leadership of village heads in development. This research assumes that this gap is mainly caused by differences in the leadership competence of village heads in different regions. Sekapuk Village, Ujungpangkah Subdistrict, Gresik Regency, East Java Province, won the first Brilliant Village ranking in 2020 (Prayitno, 2024). Then the community considers that the performance of the bureaucracy in public services is still low, by listening to the voice of the community, the village government can be more responsive and adaptive to local conditions and needs. Research aims to analyse local political communication strategies carried out by village governments in improving the performance of village public services (Raharja, et al, 2024). As well as research that aims to analyse the village

expansion model for village governance and improving the quality of public services (Hidayat, et al, 2024).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Governance

According to the World Bank (2013), governance is the process by which power and responsibility are organised in the management of economic and social resources for sustainable development.

The concepts of governance from good governance, sound governance, dynamic governance, and open government are reference concepts that are considered to be able to manage government activities properly. Any concept of governance adopted implies rejecting various forms of government activities based on authoritarian activities, corruption, collusion, and nepotism which will open up opportunities for other malicious acts in carrying out government activities.

➤ According to Bruhn (2023), Management is :

"A process that helps formulate organisational policies and objectives or a process that provides oversight of all matters involved in implementing policies and achieving objectives".

➤ Meanwhile, according to Byrnes (2022), Management is:

"The process, method, making of management that helps formulate organisational policies and objectives or that provides supervision of all matters involved in implementing policies and achieving goals by using other people's energy".

In Law No. 28 of 1998 concerning Clean and Free State Administration from Corruption, Collusion and Nepotism regarding the general principles of good state governance Governance cannot be separated from the basic principles of good governance, namely transparency, participation, accountability and coordination as the main elements in (Chusniah, et al., 2021).

- Transparency is the process of openness to convey activities carried out so that outsiders (including local communities, business actors, and other government agencies) can monitor and pay attention to these activities. facilitating access to information is the most important thing to inform and encourage community participation in forest resource management.
- Participation (inclusiveness) is the process of involving as many stakeholders as possible in policy making. Diverse input from various parties in the policy-making process to consider various issues, perspectives, and alternative options in solving a problem.
- Accountability is a responsibility/liability mechanism for policy makers with the stakeholders they serve. The existence of an accountability mechanism provides an opportunity for stakeholders to request explanations and accountability if there are things that are not in accordance with the consensus in the implementation of governance in the public sector.

- Coordination is a mechanism that ensures the extent to which other parties (especially government institutions) that have an interest in the public sector, have the same objectives reflected in their work programmes.

B. Public Service

Harbani Pasolong 2007 quoted from Witesman (2024) some can be defined "primarily as the activities of individuals, groups or organisations, directly or indirectly to meet their needs". According to Kim and Kim (2024), "services respond to administrative needs that only those who use services can satisfy and have access to the services they need".

➤ A more Detailed Definition is given by Goundar (2021), Namely

"That services are employees or other elements provided by consumers and companies that provide services

for the purpose of solving consumer/customer problems. Service levels and public satisfaction are performance measures. These measures aim to achieve the objectives of the public service agency without taking into account the cost, effort and time spent in providing services."

C. Framework

Public service governance is a system for the community that needs to guarantee the fulfilment of its rights to public services and ensure the protection of public services. The public service system has linked indicators to determine service effectiveness. Governance and effectiveness of public services can be realised if service process indicators can have a positive impact. Therefore, the author imagines using the following theory to find out the Governance of the Gantarang Village Government, Central Sinjai District in Improving Public Services.

Fig 1 Public Service Governance Framework, Qualitative Comparative analysis of Collaborative Governance Structures, (Molenveld, et al, 2021)

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This type of research is descriptive research by looking for facts with the right interpretation. The approach used is a qualitative approach, meaning that the data collected is not in the form of numbers, but the data comes from interview scripts, field notes, personal documentation, memos, and other official documentation (McNulty, et al, 2013). This

research will be carried out at the Gantarang Village Office, Central Sinjai District, Sinjai Regency, The research time was carried out for 45 days starting from the issuance of a research permit from the Muhammadiyah Sinjai University campus and the sinjai Regency PTSP office. Data collection techniques with observation, interviews and documentation. Data analysis techniques by means of data reduction, data presentation and conclusion drawing.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Village Government Governance in Improving Public Services

The need for good and correct public service governance is expected by organisations in supporting work professionalism and smooth office administration as well as in the village of Gantarang, the Governance of the Gantarang Village Government, Central Sinjai District is also needed in order to realize good public services.

As in Law No. 28 of 1998 concerning State Administration that is Clean and Free from Corruption, Collusion and Nepotism regarding the general principles of good state governance, governance cannot be separated from the basic principles of good governance, namely transparency, participation, accountability and coordination as the main elements.

➤ Transparency

Transparency is the process of openly communicating activities so that outsiders (including local communities, businesses, and other government agencies) can monitor and pay attention to these activities. Facilitating access to information is paramount to informing and encouraging community participation in resource management. The components of transparency include comprehensiveness of information, timeliness of information services, availability of information to the public, and efforts to ensure information reaches vulnerable groups. This is also done in Gantarang Village, Sinjai Tengah Sub-District, in providing information transparency to the community. This is in line with the results of an interview on (25/7/2024) with the head of Gantarang Village (I) who said that:

"Regarding the transparency point, the village government strongly upholds transparency, accountability, equality. Fairness and sticking to the rules or policies that apply, therefore we always convey every activity that will be carried out to the community, such as installing budget transparency boards and service flows and lines".

From the observations that have been made, it is true that there is transparency carried out by the village government. This is also in line with the results of an interview with the village secretary (A) on 25 July 2024 who said that:

"Transparency in Gantarang Village is going well and it is mandatory for us in the village to provide transparency to the community, why because it is very necessary not only in terms of services, even in terms of development, there must be transparency to the community so that what is the input and expectations of the community can be realised, even when talking about services, the service here is very easy and fast when the community needs something such as a cover letter and so on, just go via wabsab before going to the office to take the necessary requirements so that when going to the office what is taken care of by the community is already available".

In line with the research results, the findings underscore the ways in which public leaders communicate constructively even with opposition parties in the village governance structure and end up with the advancement of development in the region. Therefore, this study concludes that transformative public leadership is recommended for village development in the region. Keywords: Public Leadership; Good Local Governance; Village Development (Prayitno, 2024).

➤ Participation

Participation (inclusiveness) is the process of involving as many stakeholders as possible in policy making. Diverse input from various parties in the policy-making process to consider various issues, perspectives, and alternative options in solving a problem. The participation process opens up opportunities for policy-making to gain new knowledge, integrate public expectations into the policy-making process, as well as anticipate social conflicts that may arise.

From the above, it can be concluded that the level of community participation in Gantarang Village is relatively good, this can be seen from the results of observations and observations as well as interviews conducted with the head of Gantarang Village (I) on 25 August 2024 who said that:

"That the first step that must be taken and what we do is involve the community in the village deliberation or musdus which involves three hamlets owned by the village of Gantarang then all representatives are given the opportunity to submit proposals and suggestions from each hamlet that is present".

Based on the above, it can be concluded that community participation in Gantarang Village, Sinjai Tengah District is classified as good when viewed from the participation indicator, this is also justified by the Village Secretary (A) as in the results of an interview conducted on 25 July 2024 who said that:

"So in essence we in the village government have carried out our duties and functions to provide good service to the community and of course we are not closed from suggestions and input from the community, when there are things conveyed by the community related to services that do not violate the applicable rules then we are legitimate to carry out what is the input and of course we are open to all parties or people who need information, including we also involve the community in determining village policies".

In line with the research results, strategies such as increasing transparency through various communication channels, involving the community through village meetings and discussion forums, and using digital technology can accelerate interaction and ensure citizen engagement. Improving the competence of village officials in terms of communication skills and public service ethics is also crucial to creating responsive and accountable services. Promotion of village programme results and achievements can strengthen community trust and encourage active participation in development. However, challenges such as

limited resources, policy mismatches between villages and the centre, slow bureaucratic processes, and local political dynamics such as group rivalries and political interventions, still hamper the effectiveness of public services. Low levels of community participation in decision-making and oversight also reduce ownership and responsibility for village programmes, leading to dissatisfaction and reduced programme effectiveness (Raharja, et al., 2024).

➤ *Accountability*

Accountability is a responsibility / liability mechanism for policy makers with the stakeholders they serve. The existence of an accountability mechanism provides an opportunity for stakeholders to request explanations and accountability if there are things that are not in accordance with the consensus in the implementation of governance in the public sector. As well as in the village of Gantarang, Sinjai Tengah sub-district also applies the principle of accountability well, this can be seen from the results of an interview with the head of the Gantarang village (I) on 3 August 2024 who said that:

"So we continue to maintain accountability in the use of village funds to improve public services with the transparency that is carried out to guarantee access or freedom to every member of the gantarang village community to obtain information about the implementation of programmes by the village government, besides that, of course, we are accountable for every activity we carry out as well as possible".

Based on the above, it can be concluded that the accountability of the Gantarang Village government, Central Sinjai sub-district, is classified as good when viewed from the accountability indicator, this is also justified by the Village Secretary (A) as in the results of interviews conducted on 3 August 2024 who said that:

"Every thing we do, especially activities that use the village budget, of course we are well accountable not only administratively but also morally".

In line with the results of research using 122 respondents of village officials in North Lombok Regency in 2022, it shows that the village expansion model (objectivity, subjectivity and psychology) improves village governance (accountability, transparency, openness and rule of law) and the quality of public services (comfort, security, reliability, personnel attention, problem-solving approach, fairness, fiscal responsibility, and citizen influence). In addition, good village governance can strengthen the quality of public services. This research implies that the model of village expansion used in participatory development planning is to strengthen strengths to overcome weaknesses (Hidayat, et al., 2024).

➤ *Coordination*

Coordination is a mechanism that ensures the extent to which other parties (especially government institutions) that have an interest in the public sector, have common goals that are reflected in their work programmes. There are

several government agencies that have authority that intersects directly with public management, and generally the lack of coordination is the main factor that causes inefficiency and effectiveness of governance in the government sector. As seen from the results of an interview with the head of Gantarang Village, Central Sinjai Sub-district (I) during an interview on 3 August 2024 who said that:

"Coordination is very important for the village government and the regency government so that there is no miscommunication in the process of implementing public service governance in the village. Then the concrete steps taken by the village head in carrying out communication with several stakeholders involved, such as the BPD, hamlet heads and other related agencies, namely at the beginning of each year a meeting or meeting will be scheduled, we invite all community leaders, BPD, hamlet heads, youth leaders, women leaders and discuss what future development plans are to improve the quality of the Gantarang village that he owns".

In addition, the secretary of Gantarang Village (A) during an interview on 3 August 2024 was in line with the above statement by saying that:

"Coordination is real that it is very important to be carried out in all elements and all related parties because in developing the village it must be together so suggestions and responses will not work if there is no coordination from all parties involved in it, be it the role of the village government, the village head, the village secretary and all staff and ranks as well as education personnel in the village and all elements in it and must actually coordinate between sectors, so so far it has been very far and very often coordination activities have been carried out. Concrete steps have also been taken to ensure good coordination between related institutions, for example, education personnel from pre-school to kindergarten have been budgeted by the village and how then those involved are not just working in the sense that they have received incentives for what they are doing, besides that, before determining the programmes that will be budgeted and will be used as priority programmes, of course we conduct musdus, and musrebang, besides that we also provide assistance to agencies related to the programmes that we will carry out".

In line with the results of the research, the author took the initiative to conduct socialisation to village officials to improve the quality of public services. During the two-week to one-month service, the author had a realistic target, which was that village officials could master the internet. In the first week and part of the second week, the author conducted socialisation on how to use technology properly, the author taught basic things until village officials could operate the technology they had. In the final stage, the author recruited stakeholders to create websites for the three villages above in order to serve the village community digitally (Prilosadoso, et al., 2024). Good and responsible governance cannot be realised without the participation and support of the community towards the desired governance. The

enormous potential and resources of the community if utilised properly will make a significant contribution to community and village development. Various experiences have shown that governance and development without community participation will experience many difficulties. Therefore, government actors must realise that the community must be involved in every stage of government and development programmes. The community is an irreplaceable stakeholder because of its strategic role and potential for the continuity of government.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of research conducted in Gantarang Village, Central Sinjai District, with the title Governance of the Gantarang Village Government, Central Sinjai Subdistrict. In Improving Public Services. this research can be concluded that governance of Gantarang Village, Central Sinjai District in improving public services shows positive results. improving public services shows positive results. Of the four indicators that are the focus of research, namely Transparency, Participation, Accountability, and Coordination, all show good and good performance, This is evidenced by the results of researchers' interviews with several informants who have been previously determined. have been previously determined. This is reflected in the active involvement of all stakeholders, ranging from the Village Head, Village Secretary, Chairman of the BPD, Head of Hamlet to the community in the decision-making process and the implementation of work programmes in the village. work programmes in the village. Information disclosure, active community participation, and accountability mechanisms were implemented. accountability mechanisms that are well implemented are key factors in the success of the in the success of Gantarang Village governance in improving the quality of public services in the village. quality of public services in the village.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Azzahra, A. (2023). Implementation Of Good Governance in Public Services at Local Government. *International Journal of Social Service and Research*, 3(7), 1899-1906. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.46799/ijssr.v3i7.594>
- [2]. Bruhn, M. (2023). Quality management for services. *Springer Books*.
- [3]. Byrnes, W. J. (2022). *Management and the Arts*. Routledge.
- [4]. Chusniah, N., Sudarsono, S., Nurjaya, I. N., & Madjid, A. (2021). Meaning and Functions of State Administrative Assets Reports in a Clean and Free Country Management of Colusion, Corruption and Nepotism. *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, 8(12), 257-261. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.18415/ijmmu.v8i12.3278>
- [5]. Djou, S. H. N., Darman, D., Tueno, A., Gaib, S. A., Dulupi, S. N., & Darise, M. (2023). Analysis of Determinants of Village Administrative Service Quality. *West Science Business and Management*, 1(03), 99-106. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.58812/wsbm.v1i03.77>
- [6]. Goundar, S. (Ed.). (2021). *e-Services*. BoD–Books on Demand.
- [7]. Hidayat, R., Nurdin, N., Madjid, U., & Tahir, M. I. (2024). The Village Expansion Model for Village Governance and Public Service Improvement in North Lombok Regency. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science (2147-4478)*, 13(2), 253-264. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v13i2.3246>
- [8]. Honig, D. (2022). Managing for motivation as public performance improvement strategy in education & far beyond. *CID Faculty Working Paper Series*. <https://dash.harvard.edu/handle/1/37371435>
- [9]. Junaedi, J. (2023). Implementation Of Village Governance Based On Principles Of Good Governance Of Public Service In Indonesia. *International Journal of Business, Law, and Education*, 4(1), 249-266. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.56442/ijble.v4i1.160>
- [10]. Kim, S. H., & Kim, S. (2024). Trust and public service motivation. *Public Performance & Management Review*, 1-20. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.1080/15309576.2024.2377595>
- [11]. Maidin R, Rajamemang, Nurdin M, Putera W, Aliza N, Qalsum AT, Yahya IL. Implementation of the Targeted Electricity Subsidy Policy at the Office of PT. PLN (Persero) ULP Sinjai. *International Journal of Public Administration and Management Research*. 2022 Dec 12;8(3):29-41. DOI: 10.36758/ijpamr, <http://www.journals.rcmss.com/index.php/ijpamr/article/view/720>
- [12]. McNulty, T., Zattoni, A., & Douglas, T. (2013). Developing corporate governance research through qualitative methods: A review of previous studies. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 21(2), 183-198. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.1111/corg.12006>
- [13]. Molenveld, A., Voorberg, W., Van Buuren, A., & Hagen, L. (2021). A qualitative comparative analysis of collaborative governance structures as applied in urban gardens. *Public Management Review*, 23(11), 1683-1704. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.1080/14719037.2021.1879912>
- [14]. Prayitno, A. (2024). LOCAL POLITICAL COMMUNICATION STRATEGY IN IMPROVING VILLAGE PUBLIC SERVICE PERFORMANCE. *Jurnal Wacana Politik*, 9(3). DOI : [10.24198/jwp.v9i3.56844](https://doi.org/10.24198/jwp.v9i3.56844)
- [15]. Prilosadoso, B. H., Salampessy, M., Yahya, A. S., Afrizal, D., & Mado, Y. J. (2024). Socialization of Improving the Quality of Public Services Through Digital-Based Integrated Village Governance in Villages. *Journal Of Human And Education (JAHE)*, 4(4), 1025-1030. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.31004/jh.v4i4.1418>

- [16]. Putera W, Iriani N, Julian SF, Rahman A, Suciarti R. Digital Business Development Strategy as a Determinant of Business Competitiveness Through E-Commerce of MSMEs Products in Indonesia. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*. 2023 Nov 1;1(6):804-29. DOI : [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(6\).79](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(6).79)
- [17]. Raharja, W. T., Nurany, F., Subagio, D. P. W., & Bustami, M. R. (2024). The Void in Local Governance for Rural Development: Understanding Public Leadership in Village Transformation in Indonesia. *Journal of Governance*, 9(3), 394-410. DOI : <http://dx.doi.org/10.31506/jog.v9i3.22807>
- [18]. Rajamemang AM, Nurdin M, Putera W, Wahyuti AT. Effectiveness of Licensing Services for Issuing Business Identification Numbers Through the Oss-Rba System at the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office of Sinjai Regency, THE American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (THE AJHSSR), Vol6(2), (pp.63-71), DOI: <https://doi.org/10.56805/ajhss>
- [19]. Rajamemang, Qalsum AT, Maidin AM, Putera W, Abd Rasyid R. Human Resources Improvement Program Through Women Empowerment. *International Journal of Public Administration and Management Research*. 2024 Aug 14;10(4):59-67. DOI: 10.36758/ijpamr, <http://www.journals.rcmss.com/index.php/ijpamr/article/view/1052>
- [20]. Reddy, V., & Brumpton, L. (2021). Digital-driven service improvement during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Paediatrics and Child Health*, 31(5), 220-222. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paed.2021.02.006>
- [21]. Saputra, I., Sandung, C. L., Amelia, V., & Sadriani, A. (2024). The Influence of the APBDes on Road Construction in Gantarang Village, Sinjai District. *Formosa Journal of Applied Sciences*, 3(3), 959-966. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.55927/fjas.v3i3.8554>
- [22]. Witesman, E. M., Walters, L., & Christensen, R. K. (2024). Creating a public service topology: Mapping public service motivation, public service ethos, and public service values. *Public Administration*, 102(2), 540-579. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.1111/padm.12939>
- [23]. World Bank Group. (2013). *Global financial development report 2014: Financial inclusion* (Vol. 2). World Bank Publications.
- [24]. Yustisia, T. V. (2015). *Undang-Undang Nomor 6 Tahun 2014 Tentang Desa dan Peraturan Terkait*. Visimedia.